

BASIC METHODOLOGIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

¹Dushatova Shohsanam Baxtiyor qizi

FarDU o'qituvchi, sh.dushatova @pf.fdu.uz,

²Norinboeva Durdonaxon Janobiddin qizi

FarDU 3-bosqich talabasi, durdonakhonnorinboeva@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

A university student must not only have a high level of reading, writing and translating in English, but also must be able to see English in the context of another culture, the goals of teaching a foreign language - social demand, social order, conditions, the policy-driven goals of foreign language teaching can contribute to the development and progress of society.

You have read the rules of grammar or they have been explained to you; you translated the sentences and subsequent paragraphs from Latin and into Latin; you read Cicero or Caesar or Virgil and translated the texts into English - you probably read it aloud in class. Through these readings and translations, you have also learned more complex grammatical constructions. Unfortunately, you never learned to speak, but to be fair, it would be difficult to practice speaking these languages without native speakers. For the longest time, it was also used in teaching modern foreign languages. In a teacher-directed class, the teacher would explain grammar rules in the native language, followed by translation exercises with fill-in-the-blank or verb conjugation or noun conjugation. Speaking, when it occurred, was in the context of performing these exercises orally and could only consist of words or phrases. There was no attempt at "real" communication. How to organize a grammar-translation lesson? You give your readers a brief introduction in the target language. You introduce new vocabulary and give your students time to translate the passage. The new material in the passage may be a new case, a new verb tense, or a more complex grammatical construction.

You explain them to your students as you work with them through the material. Then you give your students a series of translated sentences or a short paragraph in their native language and they translate it into the target language for homework. The direct method, also called the natural approach, is in many respects the opposite of the grammar-translation method. In this class, the mother tongue is strictly forbidden and grammar (grammatical explanation) disappears in favor of induction, where students must make the rules for themselves. Students are always encouraged to speak, which is best done in student-centered classes. In theory, students learn a foreign language as naturally as they learned their native language as a child, and automatic answers to questions become instinctive. The focus was always on natural language, and habit formation was the key to learning. When students make

mistakes, teachers politely correct them. He was praised for his correct use of language. Thus, students should be able to identify the grammar rule for themselves. While the ideas are interesting, in practice this is a short-lived theory, the success of teaching L2 grammar through induction is unproven, and schools cannot provide a fully immersive environment. What would be the direct method or natural approach activity? It can be as simple as the teacher asking a question, the students answering, and then correcting or praising.

This teacher can read the passage aloud, give it to the students, and then read it aloud so that through repetition and correction, the students can have their parents read the patterns to the children can understand or she might ask students to rewrite the paragraph in their own words, again with correction or praise. Currently, students learning English are offered several methods. One of them is the main method. For this, it is necessary to study at least 2-3 years, study grammar in depth. This method is mainly used in the training of professional translators. Which is based on learning a language as a real and complete means of communication. Currently, the fundamental method has not changed its purpose, but many other methods have competed with the fundamental method. The most important thing in learning a language is how accurate the information is. A university student must not only excel in reading, writing and translating English, but must also see English in the context of other people's cultures. An English teacher should pay attention to this in the process of language teaching. In addition to the textbook, Headway Pronunciation is also included to improve pronunciation.

Another popular method of teaching English in today's fast-paced world is the "intensive method". A teacher who uses this method mainly uses dialogues as a weapon. It is impossible to learn English intensively in 2 weeks, but hardworking, self-motivated students can easily learn the language in 3 months. Another practical help for students in learning a language is foreign language programs broadcast on television, where the listener listens live and has the opportunity to test his knowledge in practice. They can also motivate the student to learn the language faster. The main goal is to help students acquire knowledge independently. In conclusion, it can be said that since there are various educational institutions in our country, a special methodology for teaching foreign languages has been developed for the purpose of teaching in them. This will be appropriate. Advanced pedagogical technologies are used in the teaching of foreign languages in our country, and the educational process is adapted to international standards. In the process of training specialists in all areas, it is important to give priority to the educational system, including the introduction of new technologies and mechanisms for teaching foreign languages. After all, communication, spiritual and other relations between peoples are expressed through language. Research on teaching foreign languages to students of non-native higher education institutions in the world is being conducted in the following priority areas: improvement of pedagogical mechanisms of teaching foreign languages to students based on European CEFR requirements; teaching content, educational technologies, strengthening the objectivity of control, organizing independent education in the classroom and outside the classroom.

The goals of teaching a foreign language goals of teaching foreign languages depend on the progress and development of society. Teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions has its own goals, and all foreign language teachers should clarify this in advance.

As scientists O. Hoshimov and I. Yakubov stated in the book "Methods of teaching English English", "The goals of teaching a foreign language determine the content, tools, methods and principles of teaching." In this section, I considered the main FLT. The methods and theory of language used in the university until now and the doctrines based on them, their main features, activities and methods, foundations and declines, as well as a general evaluation of their activities are given. The following methods are analyzed: Grammar-translation method, Structural methods and communicative approach. After some attention to innovation in the field, task-based and process models are proposed as alternatives. Finally, a link is made between curriculum innovation and change and teacher development. Knowing different methods will give foreign language teachers a better understanding of their own perspectives on pedagogical issues and classroom practice, and in addition, it will help them understand the process that FLT has undergone, particularly in this century. The different methods analyzed in this section have a common understanding of how to learn a foreign language as a process of acquiring its structure or patterns through habit formation. We will examine the approach, as well as the origin and further development of these methods: the oral or situational approach and the audiolingual method. In conclusion, it can be said that the methodology of teaching children in primary school should be based on the following principles:

- Learning through interaction and communication with people.
- The most individual approach to both the presentation of material to students and evaluation.
- Interesting, useful, fresh and new information as a basis for the lesson.
- increasing awareness and responsibility for their results.
- Integration of foreign language with other subjects.
- You can be most successful by applying the above rules teacher.

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